

VALIDITY AND PROSPECTS OF STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT IN
SMALL AND MEDIUM-SIZED BUSINESSES

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Abstract: Small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) are an important component of the economy, and their strategic management is of urgent importance. This article analyzes the importance, relevance and prospects of strategic management in SMEs. SMEs need to apply strategic planning and management approaches to effectively manage their activities, increase their competitiveness and adapt to market demands. Strategic management allows SMEs to optimally allocate resources, manage risks and introduce innovations. The article examines the main principles, problems and future prospects of strategic management for SMEs.

Keywords: Small and medium business, strategic management, competitiveness, innovation, resource management, risk management, strategic planning, adaptation to market requirements, efficiency, economic development.

Introduction. Small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) are an important component of the economy, which plays an important role in the economic development of countries, creating jobs and introducing innovations. SMEs are often characterized by flexibility, agility and innovative approaches compared to large enterprises. However, their success often depends on strategic management. This article analyzes the relevance, main principles, problems and prospects of strategic management in SMEs.

The Importance of Strategic Management:

Increasing competitiveness: SMEs often have limited resources, so strategic management is important to increase their competitiveness. Through strategic planning, SMEs can identify their strengths and weaknesses and gain an advantage over their competitors.

Adapting to market demands: As market conditions change rapidly, SMEs need to update their strategies quickly. With the help of strategic management, SMEs have the opportunity to study market requirements, identify customer needs and adapt their products or services.

Optimal allocation of resources: SMEs often have limited financial and human resources. With the help of strategic management, opportunities for optimal allocation of resources and their effective management are created.

Risk Management: SMEs face many risks, including economic, political and social risks. Strategic management facilitates risk identification, assessment and management processes.

Basic Principles of Strategic Management:

Vision and Mission: SMEs need to have a clear vision and mission that defines their operations. It helps in setting their strategic goals.

Analysis and Evaluation: SWOT analysis (Strengths and Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats) is an important tool in the strategic planning process for SMEs. Through this analysis, SMEs will be able to assess their situation and formulate their strategies.

Planning: The strategic planning process is important for SMEs in setting long-term goals and determining how to achieve them.

Implementation and Monitoring: After strategic planning, the process of monitoring the implementation and results of the plans is important. This allows SMEs to change and improve their strategies.

Problems of Strategic Management in SMEs:

Limited resources: SMEs are often limited in terms of financial and human resources, which complicates the strategic planning and implementation processes.

Fluctuating market conditions: Rapidly changing market conditions pose challenges for SMEs. They need to update their strategy quickly.

Lack of innovation capacity: SMEs often face difficulties in introducing innovations, which reduces their competitiveness.

Lack of management experience: SMEs often lack experienced managers, which complicates strategic management processes.

Prospects:

Prospects of strategic management in small and medium-sized businesses are expected to develop in the following directions:

Digital transformation: SMEs can improve their strategic management processes by implementing digital technologies. This, in turn, helps to improve efficiency and create new market opportunities.

Innovative Approaches: SMEs seek to increase their competitiveness by introducing innovations and developing new products.

Sustainability: SMEs can increase social and environmental responsibility by incorporating sustainability principles into their strategies.

International markets: SMEs can diversify their activities by expanding cooperation with international markets.

Conclusion. In small and medium-sized businesses, strategic management is of urgent importance and is necessary for their successful operation. Through strategic planning, SMEs have the opportunity to effectively manage their resources, increase their competitiveness and adapt to market conditions. Innovation and risk management are important tasks for SMEs. In the future, SMEs are expected to make their activities more efficient and competitive by further developing strategic management and implementing digital transformation processes..

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